

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of motivation and leadership style on employee performance at Menzies school of health research Timor-Leste

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Abstract

The research aimed to analyze the influence of work motivation and leadership style on employee performance at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste. Through multiple linear regression analysis using SPSS 29.0 software. The study employed a quantitative approach with primary data collected via questionnaires distributed to the entire employee population, yielding 55 responses out of 63 distributed questionnaires. Data analysis involved validity and reliability tests, followed by multiple linear regression analysis after classical assumption tests. Results indicated that work motivation and leadership style, when considered simultaneously, significantly influence employee performance. Specifically, the work motivation variable and leadership style variable both showed significant effects on employee performance. Additionally, the T-test results revealed that both the work motivation variable and leadership style variable individually have significant influences on employee performance, further highlighting their importance in enhancing organizational outcomes. The findings suggest that employees at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste are motivated by positive social interactions and encouragement from the company, while leadership fosters employee engagement through involvement in decision-making and supportive guidance. Overall, the study emphasizes how crucial of both work motivation and leadership style in improving employee performance in the context of the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste.

Keywords: Work Performance; Work Motivation; Leadership Styles; Performance Appraisal; Menzies Timor-Leste

1. Introduction

Human resources play a crucial part in any organization because through human roles enable employees to collaborate and engage with one another to accomplish goals by utilizing all of available resources. The most crucial resource for a business is its workforce or human resources. Human resources are an organization's driving power, and they are regarded as a firm asset that must be owned as a way to train and build their talents. Human resources are something that must be available as a way to meet the aims and purpose of the target firm or institution. Human resources are also an essential component in achieving the company's long-term objectives and expectations (1). Human resources that can be managed well and correctly by the company will provide benefits to the organization, such as obtaining the organization's vision and mission well, achieving profits based to targets. An organization's ability to succeed is significantly impacted by employee performance or productivity, therefore, optimizing human resources is a major concern for organizations that want to maximize their performance (2). Of doubt, an organization needs outstanding employee performance to survive.

Performance measures a staff capacity to do tasks in a way that aligns with their duties, and responsibilities both regarding of both the amount and quality of the work. Employee performance is something that institutions should take seriously since it has a direct impact on the accomplishment of corporate objectives and the capacity of an institution to prosper and endure in an unstable and constantly evolving global marketplace. Good employee performance is highly

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anticipated by the business. The company's overall productivity will rise with more high-performing employee, ensuring the company's survival and the achievement of all objectives. According to (3), there are various variables that is able to influences staff productivity or performance, including leadership style and employee work motivation. Leadership style and job motivation are two characteristics that might have an impact on employee performance. Employee performance is inextricably linked to the leader's function, but employees require encouragement to work (4). Leadership style and work motivation are important concerns not only for private organizations or ministerial, but also for Menzies Timor-Leste - School of Health Research, which provides it strengthens health systems' ability to respond to infectious disease issues around Timor-Leste.

In Timor-Leste workplaces, disciplinary procedures are implemented to enhance employee behavior and influence the behavior of others. According to (5), they can foster a cooperative workplace culture, improve industrial relations, and boost employee morale. Several institutional organizations in Timor-Leste struggle with a lack of attendance and motivation. The absence of ability frequently emerges in numerous ways, which is expected includes: 1) many employees might find it difficult to maintain constant attendance, resulting in performance interruptions and project postponements. Absenteeism can result from a number of causes, like as issues with transportation, health concerns, or particular circumstances. 2) Employees might lack motivation, that leads to less excitement, initiative, and devotion to their jobs. This lack of motivation can be attributed to a variety of causes, including imprecise expectations, restricted professional growth possibilities and inadequate acknowledgment and incentives for their job performance. 3) Employees might lack the essential skills and abilities to carry out their responsibilities successfully. This can impede organizational efficiency and creativity because staff may struggle to adjust to shifting expectations or use new technology and processes. 4) Ineffective leadership can compound concerns with attendance and motivation. Insufficient interaction, the absence of encouragement, and unpredictable methods of leadership can all lead to employee disengagement and disappointment. Addressing these issues necessitates a multidimensional strategy that involves contributing to staff development programs, building a pleasant work culture, setting clear goals and expectations, and developing strong leadership. Law No. 13 of 2003 on Manpower, Article 1 Paragraph 9, defines job training as all activities aimed at supplying, obtaining, enhancing, and developing work competencies in Indonesian Laws (6).

Based on the information from the HR department, the performance of Menzies-TL's employees is not all the best, there are still some who have not achieved exceptional performance, but most of the employees have good performance, there are also employees who have not carried out performance assessments on their performance, therefore Menzies-TL is active or provides motivation and superiors or superiors must provide support and direction so that their employees' performance can be good when they have completed one year of work at Menzies-TL.

Table 1 Factors that influence employee performance at Menzies School of Health Research Timor-Leste

Factors that influence employee performance	Employee response
Work Environment	8%
Leadership Style	28%
Training and Development	8%
Benefits and Compensation	12%
Work Motivation	44%
Total	100%

Source: Pre-survey results

The pre-survey results in Table 1 show that there are factors that affect how well employees perform. in first-place positions according to the majority of employees in Organization Menzies School of Health Research Timor-Leste, there are 44% of work motivation, followed by leadership style 28%, benefits and compensation 12%, work environment 8%, as well as training and development 8%. What came out of this pre-survey is in line with the result of the study conducted by Setiawan (7) which states that PT Assa Rent, staff performance is greatly impacted by both work motivation and leadership style. employees. Based on this phenomenon or pre-survey result, Meziess-TL must take appropriate steps and strategies to overcome leadership style and motivation, which have an impact on employee performance, because the result from employees stated that there are factors that have to improve their performance if there are impact or influence from leadership and motivation.

Based on the background description, as well as the results of the preliminary survey might be stated that work motivation and leadership style are essential for promoting improved employee performance. This has consequences for employees to improve and increase their work motivation so that the resulting performance is also good, as well as for leaders to use a dynamic and appropriate leadership style to improve employee performance. Moreover, from previous research that has different results then It is necessary to conduct research again to test again as well develop other variables that have an influence significant to performance. Considering the context of this problem, the author would like to carry out research with the title "THE INFLUENCE OF MOTIVATION AND LEADERSHIP STYLE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN MENZIES SCHOOL OF HEALTH RESEARCH TIMOR-LESTE" to undertake comprehensive further research throughout the organization.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Employee Performance

Based on (8), performance is the result of labour that is completed by an individual or collective of individuals inside a company in compliance using their specific roles and responsibilities to lawfully accomplish the goals of the organization in question, without breaking any laws, and in compliance with standards and ethics. (9).

As per (10) an employee's performance is the culmination of their combined efforts, encompassing both the quality and amount of work they accomplish in fulfilling their assigned obligations. This is also supported by the view of (11) that the ability of the employee to complete all of the duties for which he is accountable constitutes the concept of employee performance further supports this. These assignments are typically determined by success indicators that have been put into practice. It will then be known that a worker is a part of a job level. The terms for the levels can vary. Performance can be categorized as meeting, surpassing, or falling short of the goal.

2.1.1. Employee Performance Indicator

Five indicator are used by [12], for measuring the performance of individual employees, including:

- Quality: Quality of work is evaluated by how well the quality of the work of employees produced and the perfection of the task on employee skills and abilities.
- Quantity: It is the quantity created, stated in concepts like frequency of units, the quantity of finished cycles of activities.
- Punctuality: Represents the overall amount of work finished at the start of the designated period, seen out of the vantage point of cooperation with output results and maximize the period of time that can be spent on other activities.
- Effectiveness: Is a certain level of organizational use (raw material, technology, money, energy) optimized with the goal of raising each unit's performance in terms of resource usage.
- Independence: This is a certain level of a future the employee will be capable of completing its work-related functions. The level of work dedication is when employees have a commitment work alongside organizations and handle staff duties towards the company where the staff works.

2.2. Work Motivation

Motivation adapt at viewed as an alteration of energy inside oneself someone who is marked by the appearance of emotions and comes before in response to a goal. This statement contains three meanings, namely that 1) motivation initiates the occurrence of changes in energy in each individual, and 2) motivation is characterized by a person's feelings or feelings. In this case, motivation is relevant to mental and emotional problems that can determine behavior and human behavior, 3) motivation is stimulated because of a goal [13].

[14] explain that motivation is the readiness to put in significant effort to accomplish certain human demands and organizational goals that are dependent on capabilities. [15] view motivation as a system consisting of 1) needs; which are created whenever there is an imbalance between psychological and physiological, 2) Encouragement; drives, or motives (the two terms are often used interchangeably), which are formed to reduce needs, 3) Intensive; at the end of the cycle Motivation is intensive, which is in define as something that will alleviate the needs and reduce the urge.

2.2.1. Work Motivation Indicators

[16] revealed that there are 3 indicators of motivation for work, namely:

- Direction of behavior: The behavior an individual select to exhibit. Behavioral direction refers to the actions a worker decides to choose to demonstrate among the lots of potential behaviors they could demonstrate.
- Level of effort: Describes how much effort someone puts in to show the behavior he chooses. Work motivation is carried out not only so that employees show behaviors that are advantageous to the organization but also so that employees put a lot of effort for the business.
- Persistence level: The behavior that an individual chooses in facing obstacles, describes the efforts that a person will take to solve the problems they face or a person's efforts to help their colleagues in solving the problems they face.

2.3. Leadership Style

Leadership style is a manifestation of the leader's behavior and the way the leader acts concerns him competence and ability to lead. This manifestation usually forms a certain pattern or form which is called a leadership style. Leadership style is related to the leader's philosophy, skills and attitudes in carrying out his leadership duties. A leader's style is a set of actions intended to combine various business organization goals with personal objectives to fulfill specific aims [17].

Each leadership style has main characteristics, namely 1) Instructive behavior: one-way communication, the leader limits the role of subordinates, the leader is in charge of making decisions and solving problems, and work implementation is closely monitored. 2) Consultative behavior: the leader still gives quite large instructions and determines decisions that are expected to have two-way communication and provide support to subordinates. The leader is willing to listen to subordinates' complaints and feelings about decision-making. Assistance to subordinates is increased but the implementation of decisions remains with the leader. 3) Participative behavior: authority over decision-making and problem-solving processes between superiors and subordinates is equable, both superiors and followers participate in problem-solving and two-way communication and decision-making are growing, leaders are listening more intensively to their subordinates, subordinate participation in solving and decision-making is increasing. 4) Delegate behavior: the leader discusses the issues encountered with subordinates and then delegating decision-making entirely [18]

2.3.1. Leadership Style Indicators

Leadership style indicators are measured based on four leadership behaviors according to [19], namely directive/instrumental, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented. There are definitions of each leadership behavior these are as follows [20]:

- Directive leadership is a leadership behavior where the leader tells subordinates what is expected, gives instructions on what to do, and shows subordinates how to carry out tasks well. In other words, this kind of leadership provides specific direction regarding ways to complete tasks and determine schedules, regulations, and definitive standards that employees must meet.
- Supportive leadership is a leadership behavior that is friendly, friendly, and caring about the status and needs of workers.
- Participative leadership is a particular type of leadership behavior is when a leader involves their subordinates. in the process of determining decisions, asks for suggestions from subordinates, considers these suggestions before making decisions, and sometimes even allows subordinates to make their own decisions
- Achievement-oriented leadership is a type of leadership behavior where the leader helps subordinates implement goals that encourage subordinates to accept responsibility for achieving these goals and provides rewards for achieving goals.

2.4. Research Model

In accordance to the aforementioned hypotheses, Figure 1 depicts the research model:

Figure 1 Research Model

2.5. Research Design and Approach

In this research, a quantitative design was used which usually complements a deductive methodology. Existing theories benefit from a deductive approach because it guide the development of hypotheses, the choice of variables, as well as the ensuing measurements. The deductive method starts with a hypothesis that is tested after being presented as a hypotheses [21].

2.6. Type and Sources of Data

In the research, the primary data is information that is directly provided from the author. The Information is gathered by the author straight from the primary origin or the location where the research object will be conducted. The author was use questionnaires and interview results obtained from informants on the research topic as primary data. In this research the author was be utilizing secondary data for studying the influence of motivation and leadership style on employee performance. Secondary data in this research was obtained from a company which can be seen from organization documentation, book references, and other information related to research to complete and enforce the quality of research.

2.7. Data Collection Method

A questionnaire was be used in this study to gather data. The information was be collected to determine the effects of independent factors on dependent variables. The questionnaire-based collection was chosen because it enables the investigator to collect data from respondents about their opinions and knowledge of the research variables to meet the study objectives. Therefore, this questionnaire must be used to obtain valid data about motivation variables, leadership styles, and employee performance at the Menzies School of Health Research, Timor-Leste. When distributing the questionnaire, clear instructions for filling it out are also included so that it makes it is simpler for respondents to give responses.

In this research, respondents' perceptions was measured using a Likert scale. As indicated by [22], the Likert scale is a scale utilized to measure the attitudes of an individual or a group, beliefs, as well as opinions about societal issues. A Likert scale is used to transform the variables that need to be measured into indicator variables. Then these indicators are used as a beginning point of compiling instrument parts that are available for in the form of statements or questions. The 5-point Likert scale.

2.8. Population and Sample

A population is a collection of people or observational objects that have at least one thing in common. [23]. The samples in this research used 63 employees (staff) at the Menzies School of Health Research Timor-Leste. This research uses a census sampling technique, namely making the whole population the sample because the population is less than 100 people. Based on [24], if the population is less than 100 people, all members of the population can be taken as samples.

2.9. Data Analysis

2.9.1. Validity Test

'The purpose of the validity test is to evaluate the dependability or validity of survey data. When the questions adequately capture the objectives of the questionnaire, the data obtained from it is considered legitimate. The degrees

of freedom (DOF) analysis of the system allows for the identification of the greatest number of variables that must be fixed to have a defined system. Some of the DOF will be disturbances (i.e., fixed externally), while the remainder represents the maximum number of variables to control [25]. If the calculated (r) surpasses the (r) value in the table for the degree of freedom ($df = (n-2)$), then the hypothesis cannot be rejected and is considered valid.

2.9.2. Reliability Test

One method for measuring the questionnaire, which acts as an indicator of a variable or construct, is reliability testing. [26]. A questionnaire is considered reliable if an individual's responses to questions are consistent or dependable over time. To measure reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha statistical test is used. Reliability testing is a technique for assessing the functionality of software under specific conditions over a set length of time. This approach aids in the identification of software design flaws that must be corrected in order for the software to function properly. If a variable or construct has a Cronbach's Alpha value better than 0.60, it is considered reliable [27]

2.9.3. Multiple Linear Regression

A regression model that consists of multiple independent variables is called multiple linear regression. To ascertain the direction and degree multiple linear regression analysis is carried out to determine the impact of the independent factors on the dependent variable. [27]. Before the multiple linear regression model analysis, the author will be analyzing the classic assumption test as a first step. The classic assumption test is a prerequisite test conducted before further analysis of collected data [28]. In this research the classical assumption was used to as a statistical test, such as the multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, normalcy, and linearity tests, that is used to ascertain or investigate the relationship between variables.

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

Remarks: Y = Employee Performance; a = Consonant; $b_1 b_2$ = Regression Coefficient; X_1 = Motivation; X_2 = Leadership Style

2.9.4. Coefficient of Determination R^2

The degree to which the model explains the volatility of the dependent variable is measured using the coefficient of determination (R^2). [29]. The coefficient of determination has a value between zero and one. If the obtained (R^2) value is larger or approaches one (1), it indicates that the independent variables have a larger impact on the dependent variable. On the other hand, if the result is lower or gets close to zero (0), it indicates that the contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable is smaller. The equation to be used in this research as below:

$$r^2 = \frac{b \{n \Sigma XY - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)\}}{n \Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2}$$

Where: r^2 = coefficient of determination; n = the number of data points or sample size; X and Y = are the scores of the two variables; Σ = denotes summation.

2.9.5. Hypothesis Analysis

This examination be completed in order to ascertain whether each independent variable in the equation individually influences the value of the dependent variable [30]. The t-test examines whether the independent variables, including work motivation (X_1) and leadership style (X_2), individually impact employee performance (Y). The steps in hypothesis testing are as follows:

Formulate Hypotheses with select significance level (α) typically set at 0.05:

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): The influences effect of each independent variable (X_1 and X_2) on employee performance (Y) is not significant.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): The influences effect of at least one independent variable (X_1 or X_2) on employee performance (Y) is significant.

Use the formula below to calculate the t-statistic for each independent variable. Then, using the t-distribution table and the selected significance level (α) and degrees of freedom, find the critical value. If the calculated t-statistic's absolute value is higher than the critical value, reject the null hypothesis for that variable. If not, do not reject the null hypothesis.

$$T_{\text{value}} = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

Where: r^2 = coefficient of determination; n = the number of data points or sample size; r = correlation

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Description on Research Questionnaires'

This section explains the data collected from respondents at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste regarding work motivation, leadership style, and employee performance. Data was gathered through hardcopy and online questionnaires sent via email and WhatsApp. Staff members received questionnaires along with a letter explaining the research. Responses from 55 out of 63 employees were considered for analysis after excluding incomplete data. The questionnaire's completion time was one week, and all staff members were included in the sample.

3.2. Description on Respondents Characteristics

The respondent data from the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste reveals a gender distribution where male employees constitute a majority at 62%, while females represent 38% of the sample. Age-wise, the largest proportion falls within the 26-30 age bracket (36%), followed by 20-25-year-olds (24%), and 35-40-year-olds (20%), with smaller percentages for those aged 31-35 (16%) and over 41 (4%). Regarding length of employment, the study indicates that nearly one-third of respondents have worked for over three years (29%), followed by 2-3 years (27%), 1-2 years (24%), and less than one year (20%).

3.3. Variable Description

Table 2 Variable descriptive test results

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Motivation	55	37.00	60.00	49.6545	5.25716
Leadership Style	55	36.00	60.00	51.3818	6.74260
Work Performance	55	32.00	50.00	43.7818	4.18857
Valid N (listwise)	55				

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics for each research variable. According to Table 2, the analysis on work motivation reveals a range from 37 to 60, with an average of 49.65 and a standard deviation of 5.25. Similarly, the analysis on Leadership Style indicates values ranging from 36 to 60, with an average of 51.38 and a standard deviation of 6.74. For the Performance variable, the range is from 32 to 50, with an average of 43.78 and a standard deviation of 4.18. Notably, the Leadership Style variable demonstrates the highest average (51.38), while Performance exhibits the lowest (43.78). Additionally, the standard deviation is highest for Leadership Style (6.74) and lowest for Performance (4.18).

3.4. Validity Test Result

The study uses different variables with sets of questions. One set focuses on work motivation and leadership style with 12 questions, while another set assesses employee performance with 10 questions. To determine if the questions are valid, certain criteria are used: a confidence level of 95%, degrees of freedom of 53, and a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.266. For each question, its correlation with the total score must be higher than the correlation coefficient (r) and should be positive to be considered valid.

Table 3 Variable descriptive test results

Variable	Item	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r table	Note
Work Motivation	X1.1	0.275	0.266	Valid
	X1.2	0.452	0.266	Valid
	X1.3	0.324	0.266	Valid
	X1.4	0.392	0.266	Valid
	X1.5	0.560	0.266	Valid
	X1.6	0.408	0.266	Valid
	X1.7	0.581	0.266	Valid
	X1.8	0.629	0.266	Valid
	X1.9	0.724	0.266	Valid
	X1.10	0.577	0.266	Valid
	X1.11	0.423	0.266	Valid
	X1.12	0.578	0.266	Valid
Leadership Style	X2.1	0.587	0.266	Valid
	X2.2	0.664	0.266	Valid
	X2.3	0.679	0.266	Valid
	X2.4	0.503	0.266	Valid
	X2.5	0.600	0.266	Valid
	X2.6	0.804	0.266	Valid
	X2.7	0.678	0.266	Valid
	X2.8	0.838	0.266	Valid
	X2.9	0.687	0.266	Valid
	X2.10	0.697	0.266	Valid
	X2.11	0.598	0.266	Valid
	X2.12	0.713	0.266	Valid
Work Performance	Y1.1	0.613	0.266	Valid
	Y1.2	0.568	0.266	Valid
	Y1.3	0.600	0.266	Valid
	Y1.4	0.683	0.266	Valid
	Y1.5	0.515	0.266	Valid
	Y1.6	0.694	0.266	Valid
	Y1.7	0.647	0.266	Valid
	Y1.8	0.549	0.266	Valid
	Y1.9	0.652	0.266	Valid
	Y1.10	0.394	0.266	Valid

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Table 3. demonstrates that all indicators measuring the research variables had correlation coefficients surpassing $r = 0.266$ (the value for $n = 53$), confirming the validity of each indicator. This implies a robust positive connection between the factors represented by the indicators and the indicators themselves. Put simply, the indicators accurately capture and mirror the underlying concepts or phenomena examined in the research. Consequently, these indicators are deemed valid measures for the variables under scrutiny.

3.5. Reliability Test Result

Table 4 Reliability Test Result

Variable	Total Item	Cronbach Alpha	Note
Work Motivation	12	0.705	Reliable
Leadership Style	12	0.885	Reliable
Work Performance	10	0.772	Reliable

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

The reliability of the instrument's valid question items is assessed through reliability testing. A reliability coefficient of at least 0.60 indicates dependability. In Table 4 's findings on reliability tests, each coefficient exceeds 0.60, confirming the instrument's reliability. Specifically, the Work Motivation variable, comprising 12 questions, achieved a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.705; the Leadership Style variable, with 12 items, attained a value of 0.885; and the Work Performance variable, with 10 items, garnered a value of 0.772. These results demonstrate that all variables are reliable, affirming the suitability of the research instrument for further use.

3.6. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 5 Multiple Linear Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized	Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	18.578	4.476		4.151	0.001
Work Motivation	0.265	0.104	0.333	2.549	0.014
Leadership Style	0.234	0.081	0.377	2.890	0.006
Dependent Variable: Work Performance					

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

The regression equation's constant value of 18.578 implies that an employee's work value is 18.578 when both leadership style and work motivation are at zero. With a motivation coefficient of 0.333 and a positive value, every unit increase in motivation score results in a 0.333 increase in performance score, while the leadership coefficient of 0.377 indicates a similar increase in performance for every unit increase in leadership score. The positive multiple regression outcome suggests that enhancing work motivation and leadership style correlates with improved employee performance. This underscores the importance of leadership qualities such as being supportive, directive, and participative in fostering agency goals and capabilities, alongside encouraging initiative, support, and cultivating harmonious relationships among employees and between leaders and employees.

3.7. Coefficients of Determination (R²)

Table 6 Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.628a	0.394	.371	3.32234
a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Motivation, and Leadership style				

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

The coefficient of determination (R-squared) obtained at 39.4% indicates that work motivation and leadership style collectively explain a significant portion of the variability in employee performance at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste. This means that almost 40% of the differences in employee performance can be attributed to variations in these two factors. However, around 60.6% of the variability in performance remains unexplained by work motivation and leadership style alone, suggesting the presence of other influential factors beyond the scope of this analysis. These could include individual traits, organizational culture, external influences, and situational variables. While recognizing the importance of work motivation and leadership style, it's crucial to acknowledge the broader context and potential interactions with other elements when aiming to understand and enhance employee performance within an organization.

3.8. F-Test Result

Table 7 F-test Result

ANOVAa						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	373.407	2	186.704	16.915	0.001b
	Residual	573.975	52	11.038		
	Total	947.382	54			
Dependent Variable: Employee Performance Predictors: (Constant), Work motivation, Leadership Style Source: Processed primary data, 2024						

The results from the multiple linear regression analysis conducted using SPSS software revealed an F count of 16.915, surpassing the critical value of 3.18 at a significant probability threshold of 0.001. This indicates that the influence of both job motivation and leadership style on employee performance at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste is statistically significant. The F count being higher than the F table and the probability significantly lower than 0.05 further support this conclusion, suggesting a strong relationship between these variables and employee performance.

3.9. T-Test Result Partial

Testing via comparing the count with a table at the real level, $\alpha = 0.05$, is how the t-test is performed. If the error probability is less than 5% ($\text{sig} < 0.05$) or the t count is more than the t table ($\text{t count} > \text{t table}$), the t-test significantly affects the computation outcomes.

Table 8 T-test Result

Coefficients a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig
		B	Std. error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.578	4.476		4.151	0.001
	Work Motivation	0.265	0.104	0.333	2.549	0.014
	Leadership Style	0.234	0.081	0.377	2.890	0.006

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the analysis of Table 8, both the Work Motivation variable (X1) and the Leadership Style variable (X2) have been tested and shown to have significant influences on employee performance at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste. The t-values for both variables exceed the critical t-table value, indicating significance. Specifically, the t-value for Work Motivation (X1) is 2.549 with a significance level of 0.014, while for Leadership Style (X2), the t-value is 2.890 with a significance level of 0.006. This suggests that both factors play a role in influencing employee performance. However, the partial testing indicates that Leadership Style (X2) has a slightly stronger influence, as its t-value is higher than that of Work Motivation (X1). Direct observations from the author further support these findings. Employees at the Menzies School of Health Research in Timor-Leste exhibit high motivation, facilitated

by positive social interactions and continuous encouragement from the company. Additionally, leaders foster strong relationships with employees, involving them in decision-making processes, providing support, guidance, and clear instructions, which contributes to the impact of Leadership Style on performance.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research provides valuable insights into the influence of work motivation and leadership style on employee performance at Menzies School of Health Research Timor-Leste. The analysis revealed several important findings:

- Impact of Leadership Style. The analysis demonstrated a significant influence of leadership style on employee performance. A participative leadership approach, characterized by involving employees in decision-making processes and providing support and guidance, positively impacts employee performance.
- Significant Influence of Work Motivation: The study found a significant positive relationship between work motivation and employee performance. Motivated employees, particularly those who enjoy socializing with coworkers and receive continuous encouragement from the company, tend to perform better in their roles.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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